

New distributional records of fairyflies (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae) from rice–agroecosystems of Kerala

K.M. Rajesh¹, Shahid Bin Zeya², A.P. Ranjith¹ & *M. Nasser¹

¹*Insect Ecology and Ethology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, University of Calicut, Kerala, India.*

²*Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Uttar Pradesh, India.*

(Email: drnasher@gmail.com)

Abstract

Gonatocerus aegyptiacus Soyka, 1950, *Gonatocerus shamimi* Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986 (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae), *Anagrus* sp. are recorded from Kerala for the first time. Ten species of Mymarids are new distributional records from the rice-agroecosystems of Kerala. The samples were taken from the rice fields of Kerala using sweep net method during July 2013 - February 2015, and the collection comprises mymarids belonging to 10 species under 5 genera.

Keywords: *Mymaridae, New distribution, Rice-Agroecosystems, Kerala.*

Received: 7 November 2018; Revised: 31 December 2019; Online: 31 December 2019

Introduction

The family Mymaridae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) is one of the most distinctive families of Chalcidoidea and includes the smallest known insects and are all parasitoids of eggs laid in concealed habitats (Huber *et al.*, 2009). The members are widely distributed with 117 genera known from two subfamilies, Gonatocerinae and Mymarinae (Noyes and Valentine, 1989). Majority of them attack Auchenorrhyncha hemipteran, but Coleoptera, Psocoptera, Diptera and Orthoptera are also attacked (Huber and Rajakulendran, 1988). Members can be identified by using a combination of characters; female antennae with distinct club, head with 'H' shaped mark, protibial spur often long and curved, tarsi with 4–5 tarsomeres and metasoma either broadly or narrowly attached with mesosoma.

Systematic and biological research on the Mymaridae up until 1984 has been reviewed by Huber and Rajakulendran (1988). The major taxonomic treatises on the group are those of Debauche (1948), and Peck (1963). Further studies which should be of interest are those of Enock (1909), Girault (1911, 1912), Soyka (1950), Hincks (1960), Sahad and Hirashima

(1984) and Matthews (1986).

To date 194 species under 38 genera are reported from India (Manickavasagam and Athithya, 2018). Taxonomic studies on Indian mymarids were mainly carried out by Verma (1980), Subba Rao and Hayat (1983), Hayat (1992), Zeya and Hayat (1995), Hayat and Anis (1999 a,b,c), Hayat and Singh (2001), Hayat *et al.* (2008), Rehmat *et al.* (2009), Zeya and Khan (2011), Rameshkumar *et al.* (2011 a,b) Manickavasagam and Rameshkumar (2011, 2012), and Manickavasagam *et al.* (2011). As per Noyes (2019) only 35 species in 14 genera were reported from Kerala.

The species like other chalcid families (Eulophidae, Trichogrammatidae) are most encountered parasitoids of pest species and have potential as biological control agents against different pests belonging to Cicadellidae, Miridae, Membracidae and Chrysomelidae in different crops or in their natural environment (Noyes, 2003). These parasitoids attack eggs of insects in a variety of habitats and crops, but its efficacy appears to vary with host plant species (Graham *et al.*, 1986). Little is known about the host parasitoid association as only about one

quarter of the genera have hosts reported for them.

Studies by Forster (1847), Enock (1909), Macgill (1934), Douth (1959), Anderson & Paschke (1968), Stoner and Surber (1969), Miura (1979), Sahad (1982), Graham *et al.* (1986), Huber and Rajakulendran (1988), Norton *et al.* (1992), Conti *et al.* (1996), De Moraes and Mescher (1999), Virla (2001) and Jones (2001) reveals the importance of mymarids as parasitoids of insect pests.

In this paper, we reviewed the distribution and abundance of mymarid genera and species in rice agro-ecosystems of Kerala, south India.

Materials and Methods

The survey of mymarid parasitoids of rice fields was carried out from July 2013 to February 2015 during the Kharif (July—November) and Rabi (December—March) seasons. The samples were taken from the rice fields of 10 districts (three plots per district) by sweep net method.

Sweeping was done 25 meter along the bunds of rice field and two meter inside from edges, swept once at each step in a figure of eight. The trapped insects were collected using an aspirator and transferred to labeled bottles containing 70% ethyl alcohol. The collected specimens were dried and card mounted. Hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) was employed as the drying agent during mounting in order to avoid collapsing. Images of identified parasitoids were taken using Leica M205 A with DMC 2900 camera. Multiple images with different focal levels were combined into a single image using Leica Automontage Software V4.7. Images were edited in Adobe Photoshop to remove artifacts formed during stack processing. Distribution map was made with ArcGis software version 9.3 (ArcGIS 9.3 Improves Your Entire GIS Workflow: Enhanced Data Management, New Cartographic Tools, and More Efficient Information Sharing". *ESRI*. 2008-06-25. Archived from the original on 2008-06-30.).

Results

The aim of the present investigation is to study the species composition of Mymaridae

distributed in the rice–agro systems of Kerala. From the present survey 10 species of mymarids in five genera were collected, in which, *G. aegyptiacus*, *G. shamimi* and *Anagrus* sp. are new distributional report from Kerala. Of the ten species of mymarids collected during the present study, eight of them with the exception of *Lymaenon* species are new distributional records from rice fields of Kerala.

New distributional reports of Mymarid fauna of Rice-Agroecosystems from Kerala (Fig. 1)

1. *Gonatocerus aegyptiacus* Soyka, 1950 (Fig. 3B)

Specimen examined: INDIA: Kerala, Thrissur, Mullakkara, 22.iii.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Alappuzha, Kainakari, 5.ii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Wayanad, Kambalakkad, 8.xi.2012, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Wayanad, Kambalakkad, 6.xii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Nellikapalam, 28.xi.2013, sweep net coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Maniyoor, 7.ii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Ernakulam, Thuruthikkara, 26.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Ernakulam, Thuruthikkara, 7.iii.2014, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Kozhikode, Mundoth, 10.x.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Malappuram, Kalachal, 22.iii.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, Amaravila, 23.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.

Distribution: India: Assam (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Andhra Pradesh (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Bihar (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Jammu & Kashmir (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Karnataka (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Meghalaya (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Tamil Nadu (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Delhi (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Himachal Pradesh (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Odisha (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Puducherry (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Punjab (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Uttarakhand (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), West Bengal (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Andaman and Nicobar (Zeya *et al.*, 2014), Uttar Pradesh (Shamim and Shafee, 1984; Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986) and Kerala (Present study).

Figure 1: Distribution map of Mymaridae in Rice Agro-ecosystems of Kerala

Plant associates: Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

2. *Gonatocerus shamimi* Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986 (Fig. 3D)

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala, Palakkad, Thenur, 27.viii.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Kozhikode, Mundoth, 10.x.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, Amaravila, 23.1.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Kaively, 29.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.

Distribution: India: Bihar (Manickavasagam and Rameshkumar, 2011), Meghalaya (Zeya, 2015), Odisha (Zeya, 2015), Tamil Nadu (Manickavasagam and Rameshkumar, 2011) Uttar Pradesh (Shamim and Shafee, 1984), Andhra Pradesh (Rameshkumar and Manickavasagam, 2014), Jharkhand (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), West Bengal (Anwar and Zeya, 2012) and Kerala (Present study).

Plant associates: Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

3. *Lymaenon aureus* (Girault, 1911) (Fig. 3F)

Specimen examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kottayam, Changanassery, 25.1.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Nellikkapalam, 28.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Palakkad, Thenur 27.xii.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.

Distribution: India: Jammu & Kashmir (Narayanan, 1961), Maharashtra (Mani *et al.*, 1973), Uttar Pradesh (Shamim and Shafee, 1984) Andhra Pradesh (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Assam (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Bihar (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Himachal Pradesh (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Jharkhand (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Karnataka (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Kerala (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Odisha (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Puducherry (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Punjab (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Sikkim (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Uttarakhand (Amer *et al.*, 2017), West Bengal (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Tamil Nadu (Zeya and Hayat, 1995) and Meghalaya (Ramesh Kumar *et al.*, 2015).

Plant associates: Fabaceae: *Medicago sativa*, Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

4. *Lymaenon narayani* Subba Rao and Kaur, 1959

Specimen examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Nellikkapalam, 28.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.

Distribution: India: Uttar Pradesh (Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986), Kerala (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Andaman & Nicobar (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Andhra Pradesh (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Bihar (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Delhi (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Himachal Pradesh (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Karnataka (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Odisha (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Puducherry (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Tamil Nadu (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Uttarakhand (Amer *et al.*, 2017), and West Bengal (Amer *et al.*, 2017).

Plant associates: Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

5. *Gonatocerus longicornis* Nees, 1834 (Fig. 3C)

Specimen examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kollam, Kundara, 23.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Wayanad, Panamaram, 8.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Wayanad, Kambalakkad, 6.xii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, Amaravila, 23.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Ernakulam, Thuruthikkara, 7.iii.2014, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Kozhikode, Mundoth, 12.iv.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Thrissur, Ottappilavu, 12.v.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Kaively, 29.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Kudukkimotta, 7.ii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.

Distribution: India: Kerala (Mani *et al.*, 1973), Karnataka (Subha Rao & Hayat, 1986), Tamil Nadu (Subha Rao & Hayat, 1986), Assam (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Jammu & Kashmir (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Madhya Pradesh (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Odisha (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Uttar Pradesh (Zeya and Hayat, 1995), Jharkhand (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), Uttarakhand (Anwar and Zeya, 2012), West Bengal (Anwar and Zeya, 2012) and Andaman & Nicobar (Zeya *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 2: A. *Lymaenon munnarus* (Mani and Saraswat, 1973); B. *Mymar schwanni* Girault, 1912

Figures 3A-F: A. *Anagrus* sp.; B. *Gonatocerus aegyptiacus* Soyka, 1950; C. *Gonatocerus longicornis* Nees, 1834; D. *Gonatocerus shamimi* Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986; E. *Gonatocerus* sp.; F. *Lymaenon aureus* (Girault, 1911).

Plant associates: Betulaceae: *Corylus avellana* (Viggiani, 1974), Fabaceae: *Medicago sativa* (Pricop, 2009), Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

6. *Lymaenon munnarus* (Mani and Saraswat, 1973) (Fig. 2A)

Specimen examined: INDIA: Kerala, Pathanamthitta, Thiruvalla, 24.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, Kadakkavoor, 23.i.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Palakkad, Thenur, 27.viii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Wayanad, Kambalakkad, 6.xii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Thrissur, Ottapilavu, 12.v.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Jammu & Kashmir (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011; Amer *et al.*, 2017), Karnataka (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Kerala (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Madhya Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Maharashtra (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Tamil Nadu (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Uttar Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Himachal Pradesh (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Jharkhand (Amer *et al.*, 2017), Odisha (Amer *et al.*, 2017) and West Bengal (Amer *et al.*, 2017).

Plant associates: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

7. *Mymar schwanni* Girault, 1912 (Fig. 2B)

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala, Alappuzha, Kainakari, 5.ii.2013 sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.; INDIA: Kerala, Ernakulam, Thuruthikkara, 7.iii.2014, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.

Distribution: India: Andhra Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Karnataka (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Kerala (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Odisha (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Tamil Nadu (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Uttar Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Uttarakhand (Manickavasagam and Rameshkumar, 2011) and Puducherry (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011).

Plant associates: Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

8. *Palaeoneura bagicha* (Narayanan, Subba Rao and Kaur, 1960)

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Kaiveli, 29.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.

Distribution: Delhi (Huber, 2003), Himachal Pradesh (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Kerala (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Maharashtra (Subha Rao and Hayat, 1986), Punjab (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Tamil Nadu (Manickavasagam *et al.*, 2011), Uttar Pradesh (Hayat, 1992) Karnataka (Subha Rao, 1989), Meghalaya (Rameshkumar *et al.*, 2015), Uttarakhand (Joshi *et al.*, 2017) and Arunachal Pradesh (Amer and Zeya, 2018)..

Primary hosts: Hemiptera: Cicadellidae: *Sophonia rufofasciata* (Yang *et al.*, 2002).

Plant associates: Poaceae: *Oryza sativa* L. (Present study).

9. *Anagrus* sp. (Fig. 3A)

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Nellikkapalam, 28.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.

10. *Gonatocerus* sp. (Fig. 3E)

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala, Kannur, Nellikkapalam, 28.xi.2013, sweep net, coll. Rajesh, K.M.; INDIA: Kerala, Alappuzha, Kainakari, 5.ii.2013, sweep net, coll. Ranjith, A.P.

Gonatocerus aegyptiacus is the numerically abundant mymarid species collected and distributed in nine districts viz: Kannur, Kozhikode, Wayanad, Malappuram, Palakkad, Thrissur, Ernakulam, Alappuzha and Thiruvananthapuram. *Gonatocerus longicornis* is the second dominant species recorded in 10 districts except Kottayam, Idukki, Pathanamthitta and Palakkad. Mymarid species richness in Kannur district was the highest with eight species viz: (*G. aegyptiacus*, *G. shamimi*, *G. longicornis*, *Lymaenon aureus*, *L. narayani*, *Palaeoneura bagicha* and *Gonatocerus* sp.),

Table 1. The distribution of Mymaridae in Rice-Agroecosystems of Kerala

SI. No	Species	Place
1.	<i>Gonatocerus longicornis</i> Nees, 1834	Kollam – Kundara : 8°58'05.6"N 76°40'24.3"E Malappuram – Valanchery : 10°53'08.4"N 76°04'41.4"E Ernakulam – Thuruthikkara : 9°53'17.0"N 76°24'13.1"E Panamaram–Wayanad : 11°44'09.7"N 76°04'38.4"E Wayanad – Kambalakkadu : 11°40'31.1"N 76°04'39.3"E Thiruvananthapuram – Amaravila : 8°23'50.0"N 77°06'26.1"E Thiruvananthapuram –Kadakkavoor : 8°41'02.1"N 76°46'43.8"E Ernakulam – Thuruthikkara : 9°53'17.0"N 76°24'13.1"E Thrissur– Ottapilavu : 10°38'36.0"N 76°04'13.5"E Kozhikode – Mundoth : 11°27'04.4"N 75°45'08.9"E Kannur – Kaiveli : 12°03'00.1"N 75°19'38.5"E Alappuzha – Kainakari : 9°30'58.5"N 76°23'31.8"E Kannur – Kudukkimotta : 11°54'57.0"N 75°26'55.8"E Kasaragode – Pallikkara : 12°25'17.7"N 75°01'57.3"E

New distributional records of fairyflies from rice–agroecosystems of Kerala

2.	<i>Gonatocerus aegyptiacus</i> Soyka, 1950	<p>Thrissur– Mullakkara : 10°27'07.9"N 76°10'57.3"E</p> <p>Palakkad – Thenur : 10°47'42.5"N 76°32'26.7"E</p> <p>Ernakulam – Thuruthikkara : 9°53'17.0"N 76°24'13.1"E</p> <p>Kozhikode – Mundoth : 11°27'04.4"N 75°45'08.9"E</p> <p>Wayanad – Kambalakkad : 11°40'31.1"N 76°04'39.3"E</p> <p>Kannur – Nellikkapalam : 11°57'41.6"N 75°26'40.9"E</p> <p>Alappuzha – Kainakari : 9°30'58.5"N 76°23'31.8"E</p> <p>Thiruvananthapuram – Amaravila : 8°23'50.0"N 77°06'26.1"E</p> <p>Malappuram – Kalachal : 10°45'30.4"N 76°00'57.7"E</p> <p>Kannur – Maniyoor : 11°33'50.6"N 75°39'36.2"E</p> <p>Malappuram – Valanchery : 10°53'08.4"N 76°04'41.4"E</p>
3.	<i>Gonatocerus shamimi</i> Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986	<p>Malappuram – Valanchery : 10°53'08.4"N 76°04'41.4"E</p> <p>Palakkad – Thenur : 10°47'42.5"N 76°32'26.7"E</p> <p>Kozhikode – Mundoth : 11°27'04.4"N 75°45'08.9"E</p> <p>Thiruvananthapuram – Amaravila : 8°23'50.0"N 77°06'26.1"E</p> <p>Kannur – Kaiveli : 12°03'00.1"N 75°19'38.5"E</p>
4.	<i>Lymaenon munnarus</i> (Mani and Saraswat, 1973)	<p>Pathanamthitta – Thiruvalla : 9°22'43.9"N 76°35'18.6"E</p> <p>Thiruvananthapuram – Kadakkavoor : 8°41'02.1"N 76°46'43.8"E</p>

		Palakkad – Thenur : 10°47'42.5"N 76°32'26.7"E Wayanad – Kambalakkadu : 11°40'31.1"N 76°04'39.3"E Malappuram – Valanchery : 10°53'08.4"N 76°04'41.4"E Thirissur – Ottapilavu : 10°38'36.0"N 76°04'13.5"E Ernakulam – Thuruthikkara : 9°53'17.0"N 76°24'13.1"E
5.	<i>Lymaenon aureus</i> (Girault, 1911)	Kottayam – Changanassery : 9°25'03.0"N 76°31'26.9"E Palakkad – Thenur : 10°47'42.5"N 76°32'26.7"E Kannur – Nellikkapalam : 11°57'41.6"N 75°26'40.9"E
6.	<i>Lymaenon narayani</i> Subba Rao and Kaur, 1959	Kannur – Nellikkapalam : 11°57'41.6"N 75°26'40.9"E
7.	<i>Palaeoneura bagicha</i> (Narayanan, Subba Rao and Kaur, 1960)	Kannur– Kaiveli : 12°03'00.1"N 75°19'38.5"E
8.	<i>Mymar schwanni</i> Girault, 1912	Alappuzha – Kainakari : 9°30'58.5"N 76°23'31.8"E Ernakulam – Thuruthikkara : 9°53'17.0"N 76°24'13.1"E
9.	<i>Gonatocerus</i> sp.	Kannur – Nellikkapalam : 11°57'41.6"N 75°26'40.9"E Alappuzha – Kainakari : 9°30'58.5"N 76°23'31.8"E
10.	<i>Anagrus</i> sp.	Kannur – Nellikkapalam : 11°57'41.6"N 75°26'40.9"E

New distributional records of fairyflies from rice–agroecosystems of Kerala

followed by Alappuzha (*G. longicornis*, *G. aegyptiacus*, *Mymar schwanni*, *Anagrus* sp. and *Gonatocerus* sp.), species richness is least in Kottayam (*L. aureus* only) and Kollam (*G. longicornis* only) districts (Table 1).

Discussion

Out of the 1424 species reported from 103 genera worldwide, only 194 species under 38 genera are known from the Indian subcontinent that constitute 32.8 and 11.9 per cent of world genera and species respectively (Manickavasagam and Athithya, 2018). Manickavasagam and Athithya in 2018 constructed the very latest checklist of Indian mymarids, with five genera viz., *Allanagrus*, *Dorya*, *Platystethynium*, *Schizophragma* and *Stephanocampta* were newly recorded, four genera viz., *Cosmocomoidea*, *Lymaenon*, *Tanyxiphium* and *Zeyanus* were added during reclassification of *Gonatocerus*, 56 new species were described and 12 first reports of species were made from India. Seven species viz., *Acmopolynema shrawastianum*, *Erythmelus lygivorius*, *Gonatocerus sulphuripes*, *G. tarae*, *G. pahlgamensis*, *G. similis* and *Polynema huberi* were synonymized and one species misidentified.

Distribution status of the Mymaridae from Kerala is comparatively wider as 35 species under 14 genera were recorded earlier. Most of the mymarids were reported as solitary/gregarious egg parasitoids of the plant/leaf hoppers (Huber and Rajakulendran, 1988). Present study extended the distribution status of mymarids in the rice agroecosystems with the first report of species *G. aegyptiacus* from south India. The distribution of *G. aegyptiacus* is found to be very wide as it extended from Holarctic to the Oriental regions (Soyka, 1950; Sahad, 1982; Sahad and Hirashima, 1984; Subba Rao and Hayat, 1986; Donev, 2003).

The present study also portrays the distribution and abundance of fairyflies in the rice fields as ten species under five genera were reported exclusively from rice fields of Kerala.

Among the studied species, the speciose genus, *Gonatocerus* is numerically abundant with 26 specimens from four species. This result is well in line with the study of Rameshkumar *et al.* (2011b) as 13 species were already recorded

from the Kerala state. In addition to this the distribution of the species listed in the present study apparently confirms the biological association of the genus with the rice agroecosystems as the species *G. longicornis* and *G. shamimi* were already recorded from rice paddy ecosystems. Most of the *Gonatocerus* species are already reported from north Indian states but the extended distribution of *Gonatocerus* (*G. ater* Foerster, 1841, *G. bakrotus* Mani and Saraswat, 1973, *G. bashai* Zeya, 1995, *G. bouceki* Zeya, 1995, *G. delhiensis* (Narayanan and Subba Rao, 1961) and *G. shamimi*) indicates that the genus has a wider distribution status within the Indian subcontinent than reported earlier (Zeya and Hayat, 1995; Rameshkumar *et al.*, 2011a,b).

Despite the wide distribution of Indian *Gonatocerus*, some species are found to be endemic to south India like *G. berijamus* Mani and Saraswat, 1973 and *G. kodaiyanus* (Mani and Saraswat, 1973) (Rameshkumar *et al.*, 2011a, b). Similarly all the *Lymaenon* species collected during the present study were already recorded from the rice paddy ecosystems (Rameshkumar *et al.*, 2011b).

In 2017, Amer *et al.* conducted a survey on Indian mymarids, and they provided many new distribution reports from all over India.

As mentioned in the results the 10 species recorded in the present study from rice ecosystems of Kerala are distributed across many states of India. This study has recorded additional mymarid species as possible parasitoids of pests of rice. In addition to this *L. narayani* earlier recorded as a parasitoid of *Eucoccosterphus tuberculatus* (Hemiptera: Membracidae) (Zeya and Hayat, 1995) has now been collected from rice fields which opens up the possibility of an alternate host for the parasitoid species as membracids are usually not seen in rice fields. Additionally, more detailed survey with emphasis on host rearing will help in providing the host association of mymarids which will help to facilitate the adoption and designing of biocontrol strategies to control pests of rice using mymarids.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by Ministry of Environment, Forests and Climate

Change, New Delhi. We would like to express thanks to Dr. Santhosh S., Assistant Professor, Malabar Christian College, Kozhikode for providing facilities during photographic session. We also thankful to Mrs. Bindu, Assistant Professor in Geography, H.M. College of Science and Technology, Manjeri for her valuable help during the preparation of distribution map.

References

- Amer, F.S.K., Zeya, S.B. and Jamali, M.M. 2017. A new species of *Lymaenon* Walker (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae: Gonatocerini) from India with the country checklist and new records. *Oriental Insects* 51(4): 357-358.
- Amer, F.S.K. and Zeya, S.B. 2018. Review of the Indian species of *Palaeoneura* Waterhouse (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae). *Oriental Insects* 53(2): 191-211
DOI: [10.1080/00305316.2018.1478754](https://doi.org/10.1080/00305316.2018.1478754)
- Anderson, R.C. and Paschke, J.D. 1968. The biology and ecology of *Anaphes flavipes*, an exotic egg parasite of the cereal leaf beetle. *Annals of Entomological Society of America* 61: 1-5.
- Anwar, P.T. and Zeya, S.B., 2012. Record of some species of Mymaridae from different states of India (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). *Bionotes* 14(2): 52-53.
- Conti, E., Jones, W.A., Bin, F. and Vinson, S.B. 1996. Physical and chemical factors involved in host recognition behavior of *Anaphesiole* Girault, an egg parasitoid of *Lygus hesperus* Knight (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae; Heteroptera: Miridae). *Biological Control* 7: 10-16.
- Debauche, H.R. 1948. Étude sur les Mymarommatidae et les Mymaridae de la Belgique (Hym., Chalcidoidea). *Mémoires du Musée Royal d'Histoire Naturelle de Belgique* 108: 99.
- De Moraes, C.M. and Mescher, M.C. 1999. Interactions in entomology: Plant parasitoid interactions in tritrophic systems. *Journal of Entomological Science* 34: 31-39.
- Donev, A.D. 2003. Genera and species of Mymaridae (Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea) newly recorded to the fauna of Crete (Greece). I. Plovdivski Universitet "PaisijKhilendarski" Nauchni Trudove Biologiya Animalia 39(6): 75-76.
- Doutt, R.L. 1959. The biology of parasitic hymenopteran. *Annual Review of Entomology* 4: 161-182.
- Enock, F. 1909. New genera of British Mymaridae (Haliday). *Transactions of the Entomological Society of London* 1909: 449-459, pls XII-XIV.
- Förster, A. 1847. Ueber die Familie der Mymariden. *Linnaea Entomologica* 2: 201.
- Girault, A.A. 1911. Descriptions of North American Mymaridae with synonymic and other notes on described genera and species. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society* 37: 263.
- Girault, A.A. 1912. Australian Hymenoptera Chalcidoidea. II. The family Mymaridae with descriptions of new species. *Memoirs of the Queensland Museum* 1: 166.
- Graham, H.M., Jackson, C.G. and Debolt, W.J. 1986. *Lygus* spp. (Hemiptera: Miridae) and their parasites in agricultural areas of southern Arizona. *Environmental Entomology* 15: 132-142.
- Hayat, M. 1992. Records of some Mymaridae from India with notes (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). *Hexapoda* 4: 83-89.
- Hayat, M. and Anis, S.B. 1999a. New record of two genera *Ptilomymar* and *Himopolynema* from India: with description of two new species (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae). *Shashpa* 6: 15-22.
- Hayat, M. and Anis, S.B. 1999b. The Indian species of *Acmopolynema* with notes on *Acanthomymar* (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae). *Oriental Insects* 33: 297-313.
- Hayat, M. and Anis, S.B. 1999c. The Indian species of *Polynema* with notes on *Stephanodes reduvioli* (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae). *Oriental Insects* 33: 315-331.
- Hayat, M. and Singh, S. 2001. Description of new species of *Polynema* from India with further records of *Himopolynema hishimonus* (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae). *Shashpa* 8: 95-97.
- Hayat, M., Anis, S.B. and Khan, F.R. 2008. Descriptions of two new species of *Mymaridae* (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea)

New distributional records of fairyflies from rice–agroecosystems of Kerala

- from INDIA: with some records. *Oriental Insects* 42: 327-333.
- Hincks, W.D. 1960. Some additions to the British Mymaridae (Hym., Chalcidoidea). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 95: 211.
- Huber, J.T. and Rajakulendran, V.K. 1988. Redescription of and host-induced antennal variation in *Anaphesiole* Girault (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae), an egg parasite of Miridae (Hemiptera) in North America. *The Canadian Entomologist* 120: 893-901.
- Huber, J.T. 2003. Review of *Chaetomymar* Ogloblin, with description of a new species in the Hawaiian Islands (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae). *Journal of Hymenoptera Research* 12(1): 87.
- Huber, J.T., Viggiani, G. and Jesu, R. 2009. Order Hymenoptera, family Mymaridae. *Arthropod Fauna of the UAE* 2: 270–297.
- Jones, W.A. 2001. Classical biological control of the glassy-winged sharpshooter, pp. 50-51. *In: Proceedings of the Pierce's Disease Research Symposium*, 5-7 December, 2001, Coronado.
- Joshi, B., Singh, S. and Nautiyal, R., 2017. New distributional records of Mymaridae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Uttarakhand, India. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies* 5(3): 1809-1813.
- Macgill, E. 1934. On the biology of *Anagrus atomus* (L.) Ha: An egg parasite of the leafhopper *Erythroneura pallidifrons* Edwards. *Parasitology* 26: 57-63.
- Mani, M.S., Dubey, O.P., Kaul, B.K. and Saraswat, G.G. 1973. On some Chalcidoidea from India. *Memoirs of the School of Entomology, St. John's College, Agra* No. 2: 87-89.
- Manickavasagam, S. and Rameshkumar, A. 2011. First report of three genera of fairyflies (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) from India with description of a new species of *Dicopus* and some other records. *Zootaxa* 3094: 65.
- Manickavasagam, S., Rameshkumar, A. and Rajmohana, K. 2011. First report of four species of fairyflies from India: key to Indian species of four genera and additional distributional records of Mymaridae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). *Madras Agricultural Journal* 98(10-12): 393-408.
- Manickavasagam, S. and Rameshkumar, A. 2012. First report of *Callodicopus* Ogloblin (Mymaridae) from India and new records of some Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) from Andaman and Nicobar Islands. *Journal of Biological Control* 26(4): 321-328.
- Manickavasagam, S. and Athithya, A. 2018. An updated checklist of Mymaridae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) of India. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies* 6(4): 1654-1663.
- Matthews, M.J. 1986. The British species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae), egg parasitoids of Homoptera. *Systematic Entomology* 11: 220.
- Miura, T. 1979. On the longevity and parasitic activity of adult *Gonatocerus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae). *Bulletin Faculty Agriculture Shimane University* 13: 156-162.
- Narayanan, E.S. 1961. New record and description of new species of parasites of San Jose scale. *Proceedings of the National Institute of Sciences of India (B)* 26(supplement): 24.
- Norton, A.P., Welter, S.C., Flexner, J.L., Jackson, C.G., Debolt, W.J. and Pickel, C. 1992. Parasitism of *Lygus hesperus* (Miridae) by *Anaphes iole* (Mymaridae) and *Leiophron uniformis* (Braconidae) in California strawberries. *Biological control* 2: 131-137.
- Noyes, J.S. and Valentine, E.W. 1989. Mymaridae (Insecta: Hymenoptera). *Fauna of New Zealand* 17: 100 pages.
- Noyes, J.S. 2003. Universal Chalcidoidea Database. World Wide Web electronic publication. <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/entomology/chalcidoids/index.html> (accessed 10.10.2008).
- Noyes, J.S. 2019. Universal Chalcidoidea Database. World Wide Web electronic publication. Accessed online at <http://www.nhm.ac.uk/chalcidoids>
- Peck, O. 1963. A catalogue of the Nearctic Chalcidoidea (Insecta; Hymenoptera). *The Canadian Entomologist (Supplement)* 30: 21.

- Pricop, E. 2009. Mymarid wasps (Hymenoptera, Chalcidoidea, Fam. Mymaridae) associated with *Medicago sativa* L. (First note). Studiisi Cercetari, Universitatea din Bacau, Biologie 17: 81.
- Rehmat, T., Anis, S.B. and Hayat, M. 2009. Record of the genus *Litus* Haliday (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae) from India: with description of two species. Journal of Threatened Taxa 1: 370-374.
- Rameshkumar, A., Manickavasagam, S. and Jebanesan, A. 2011a. Diversity and new distributional records of fairyflies (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae) from the state of Kerala, India. Plant Archives 11(2): 769-774.
- Rameshkumar, A., Manickavasagam, S. and Jebanesan, A. 2011b. New distributional records of fairyflies (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae) from Pudhucherry, India. Madras Agricultural Journal 98(7-9): 279-281.
- Rameshkumar, A. and Manickavasagam, S. 2014. Records of some Mymaridae and Encyrtidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) from Andhra Pradesh, India. The Journal of Research PJTSAU 42(4):15-20.
- Rameshkumar, A., Poorani, J. and Naveen, V. 2015. Addition to the Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) of Meghalaya with special reference to Encyrtidae, Mymaridae and Aphelinidae. Journal of Biological control 29(2): 49-61.
- Sahad, K.A. 1982. Descriptions of new species of *Gonatocerus* Nees and *Anagrus* Haliday from Japan (Hymenoptera, Mymaridae). Esakia 19: 195-198.
- Sahad, K.A. and Hirashima, Y. 1984. Taxonomic studies on the genera *Gonatocerus* Nees and *Anagrus* Haliday of Japan and adjacent regions, with notes on their biology (Hymenoptera, Mymaridae). Bulletin of the Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Kyushu University 7: 1-78.
- Shamim, S.M. and Shafee, S.A. 1984. Descriptions of three new species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) from Aligarh (India). Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society 80(3): 623-624.
- Soyka, W. 1950. New and little known alaptids and mymarids from Egypt. Bulletin de la Société Fouad Ierd'Entomologie, Le Caire 34: 125.
- Stoner, A., and Surber D.E. 1969. Notes on the biology and rearing of *Anaphes ovijentatus*, a new parasite of *Lygus hesperus* in Arizona. Journal of Economic Entomology 62: 501-502.
- Subba Rao, B.R. and Hayat, M. 1983. Key to the genera of Oriental Mymaridae, with a preliminary catalog (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). Contributions of the American Entomological Institute 20: 125-150.
- Subba Rao, B.R. and Hayat, M. 1986. Family Mymaridae. (In: B.R. Subba Rao; M. Hayat (eds.) - The Chalcidoidea (Insecta: Hymenoptera) of India and the adjacent countries. Part II.). Oriental Insects 20: 186.
- Verma, M. 1980. New record of *Mymar schwanni* Girault from India (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea, Mymaridae). Journal Bombay Natural History Society 76: 536-537.
- Viggiani, G. 1974. Studies on the insect fauna of hazel. IX Notes on some Homoptera (*Ceresa bubalus* - Fbr. - *Ledraaurita* - L. - and *Cicadella viridis* - L.). Annalidella Facoltà di Scienze Agrariedella Universitàdegli Studi di Napoli Portici 7: 153-160.
- Virla, E. 2001. Notes on the biology of *Anagrus breviphragma* (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae), natural enemy of the corn leafhopper *Dalbulus maidis* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) and other plant diseases vectors in South America. BolSanidad Veg "Plagas" 27(2): 239-247.
- Yang, P., Foote, D., Alyokhin, A.V., Lenz, L. and Messing, R.H. 2002. Distribution and abundance of mymarid parasitoids (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) of *Sophonia rufofascia* Kuoh and Kuoh (Homoptera: Cicadellidae) in Hawaii. Biological Control 23(3): 237-244.
- Zeya, S.B. and Hayat, M. 1995. A revision of the Indian species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae). Oriental Insects 29: 47-160.
- Zeya, S.B. and Khan, F.R. 2011. On the species of *Gonatocerus* from different Indian States

New distributional records of fairyflies from rice–agroecosystems of Kerala

- (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae).
Bionotes 13: 11–13.
- Zeya, S.B. 2014. Description of a new species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) from India, with some records. *Journal of Insect Systematics* 1(2): 81-91.
- Zeya, S.B., Usman, S.U. and Veenakumari, K. 2014. Records of some Mymaridae from India, with description of a new species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea). *Journal of Insect Systematics* 1(1): 62-63.
- Zeya, S.B. 2015. Description of a new species of *Gonatocerus* Nees (Hymenoptera: Mymaridae) from India, with some records. *Journal of Insect Systematics* 1(2): 87.